

Studies of Physico-chemical Properties of O/W Emulsions

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Oil-in-water emulsions with water and various oils like kerosene oil, liquid paraffin and turpentine oil as external and internal phase, stabilized by protein have been prepared. Physico-chemical properties, i.e., emulsions type, specific gravity, surface tension, viscosity, conductivity and particle size of the emulsions have been measured. Low surface tension and specific gravity, high viscosity, conductivity and particle size favour emulsification and increase stability of the emulsions. As the specific gravity of the oil increases, emulsification is favoured. The surface tension, viscosity decrease while conductivity increases with increasing of the temperature.

A survey of literature reveals that various types of oil-in-water emulsions have been prepared by taking two immiscible liquids as external and internal phases stabilized by surface active materials¹⁻⁴. Use of finely divided solids⁵⁻⁶, resin Soaps⁷, water soluble gums⁸⁻⁹ and organic compounds¹⁰⁻¹¹ as surfactants has also been cited in the literature. The literature also reveals the study of various properties of these emulsions such as stability¹², demulsification¹³, globule size distribution¹⁴, inversion¹⁵, creaming¹⁶, viscosity¹⁷ etc.

The effect of oils as dispersed phase on the physico-chemical properties of the emulsions has not been thoroughly investigated upto now.

The present communication provides a set of information about the emulsification efficiency of different oils and their effect on the physico-chemical properties of the emulsions.

Experimental

In all the experiments doubly distilled kerosene oil (sp. gr. 0.79378), turpentine oil (sp. gr. 0.87458), liquid paraffin (Medical grade, viscosity 1.56 poise at 25°) and water (conductivity 1×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) were used. The gelatin (Photographic quality) and sodium chloride (BDH product) were employed.

Emulsions were prepared by agent in water method¹⁸, by using different oils as dispersed phases and water as a dispersion medium. The non-aqueous phase was added to the aqueous solution of emulsifier with constant stirring. The emulsions thus obtained were homogenized by Redimix Mixer.

Emulsion type (O/W or W/O) was determined by the dye solubility method¹⁹. Caicomine Blue (soluble in water and insoluble in oil) and Savinyl Green (soluble in oil and insoluble in water) were

added to two separate parts of each emulsion and the mixture was gently agitated. It was observed that the part to which Caicomine Blue was added, turned blue and the other part to which Savinyl Green was added remained milky white. Thus the water constituted the continuous phase and oil the dispersed phase. So the emulsions were O/W types.

Particle size was measured by Hymoptik microscope occ. 10 X, obj. 45 X and viscosity, surface tension, specific gravity and conductivity were measured by Ostwald Viscometer, drop weight method, Pyknometer and Conductance meter with 'magic eye' (WTW, German make) respectively, at different temperatures. Results are summarised in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 1—EMULSION TYPE : O/W, O/W RATIO=1 : 4
KEROSENE OIL=10 ml, GELATIN=1%, NaCl=0.45%
PARTICLE SIZE 1.5-3 μ

Sl. No.	Temp. °C	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-6}$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Specific gravity
1.	20	5.8	4.177	66.312	0.96699
2.	25	7.2	3.215	65.523	0.96402
3.	30	9.5	2.906	64.645	0.96386
4.	35	12.3	2.857	63.307	0.96350
5.	40	14.4	1.916	62.814	0.96332
6.	50	17.6	1.034	61.492	0.96314

TABLE 2—EMULSION TYPE : O/W, O/W RATIO=1 : 4
LIQUID PARAFFIN=10 ml, GELATIN=1%, NaCl=0.45%
PARTICLE SIZE 2-4.5 μ

Sl. No.	Temp. °C	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-6}$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Specific gravity
1.	20	7.8	5.122	34.516	0.98742
2.	25	9.3	4.863	33.098	0.98721
3.	30	11.6	4.075	32.874	0.98704
4.	35	14.7	3.762	31.263	0.98695
5.	40	16.5	2.514	30.714	0.98663
6.	50	19.3	1.678	29.311	0.98637

TABLE 3—EMULSION TYPE : O/W, O/W RATIO=1 : 4
TURPENTINE OIL=10 ml, GELATIN=1%, NaCl=0.45%
PARTICLE SIZE AT 20°C 3-5 μ

Sl. No.	Temp. °C	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-8}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Specific gravity
1.	20	8.4	6.962	32.106	0.99182
2.	25	10.1	5.425	31.345	0.99160
3.	30	11.5	4.175	30.273	0.99141
4.	35	15.7	3.602	29.549	0.99115
5.	40	17.4	2.437	28.751	0.99082
6.	50	20.2	1.982	27.246	0.99056

Results and Discussion

During the preparation of emulsions it was observed that when oils with different sp. gr. (K. O., Liquid Paraffin and T.O.) were employed as dispersed phase, thick and viscous emulsions were obtained which may be due to creaming.

It has been found that decrease of surface tension confers greater stability to the emulsions^{1,8}. Neogy and Ghosh²⁰ have reported that higher viscosity aids the emulsification by decreasing the mobility of the droplets constituting the dispersed phase. The present data shows that as we pass from kerosene oil (low sp. gr.) to turpentine oil (high sp. gr.) the surface tension of various O/W type emulsions decreases while viscosity increases. The decrease of surface tension and increase of viscosity indicates enhanced stability of the emulsions. It is, therefore, concluded that the increase in density of the oil employed results in the enhancement of stability of emulsions. This is to be expected as the particle size increases from kerosene oil to turpentine oil emulsions and the coarser emulsions represent a situation of maximum stability.

The conductance shows an increase as we pass from O/W system in the case of kerosene oil to O/W system for turpentine oil. As the temperature increases, conductivity also increases.

It may be concluded that although there is no visual change in the stability of the emulsions between 20° to 50°, however, the value of surface tension, viscosity and specific gravity of emulsions decrease and conductivity increases with an increase in the temperature of emulsions. It is also concluded from the above observations that low surface tension and specific gravity, high viscosity, conductivity and particle size favours emulsification and

increase the stability of emulsions. These results are in good agreement with the earlier workers²¹.

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